

EXAMINE THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE LEVELS OF LIFE SATISFACTION AND LEISURE TIME SATISFACTION OF FOREIGN STUDENTS STUDY AT ERCIYES UNIVERSITY, TURKEY

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Abstract:

The aim of the study is to examine the relationship between the levels of life satisfaction and leisure time satisfaction of foreign students study at Erciyes University. The research group totally consists of 220 foreign students, 147 of them are male and 73 of them are female students study at Erciyes University. In order to obtain lesiure time satisfaction level data, "Leisure Time Satisfaction Scale" developed by Karlı et al. In 2008 and 'Life Satisfaction Scale' developed in 1985 by Diener et al. There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of gender variance, while there was a meaningful difference between the groups according to the place they live, the sporting situation, the type of activity they attended and the way they affect their classes. There was an important difference found between the groups according to their gender, sporting activities, activity types they attended and their influence on their courses, while there was no significant difference found between the groups according to their residence status in life satisfaction levels. There was a positive relationship found between the leisure time satisfaction levels and the life satisfaction levels of the foreign students who participated in the study. As a result, as the level of satisfaction of foreign

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students who study at Erciyes University increases then their level of satisfaction also increases.

Keywords: leisure time satisfaction, life satisfaction, foreign students

1. Introduction

Nowadays, different definitions are being made about the concept of time, which is especially popular among contemporary people. Time is one of the most precious events a person has. These days, one of the problems that people often experience is a time problem. Work life, which takes a large part of people's time, leaves no free time for themselves (Mutlu, 2008). In recent years, as in all fields, the number of studies on free time and quality of life in the field of physical education and sports increased (2016) Comparison of Physical Activity Levels and Quality of Life Levels (Bitlis Province), Öztürerru (2013) The Level of Physical Activity and Quality of Life of University Employees (2016), studies of Gönülateş (2016) The Impact of Recreational Participation on Quality of Life in Different Countries, (2016) An Analysis of the Effects of Participation in Leisure Activities in the Prevention of Aggression, Violence and Hooliganism Behavior in Football Audiences, Serdar (2016) Satisfaction of Freelance Time Events and the Perceived Freedom Levels of University Students' Participation, Zerengök (2016) International Students'; Analysis of Social Cohesion Through Active Participation in Leisure Activities: An Example of Celal Bayar University and Lakot (2015) We can show these works as an example of the studies on the sense of Leisure Time and Disabilities in Physical Education Teacher Candidates.

As a word, time is 'a permanent process of events coming from past to present and continuing to the future' (Smith, 1998, Güçlü, 2001). And Leisure time is defined as the time when one is free from all necessities or connections for himself and others, and when he will deal with an activity he chooses on his own choosing, that is, the person is absolutely independent and free (Tezcan, 1993). In other words, leisure time; (Torkildsen, 2005), after fulfilling the practical needs of life (working hours, physiological needs such as eating and sleeping). As noted by Tinsley and Eldredge (1995), free time activities include; physical exercise, play, arts and cultural activities, to satisfy one's psychological needs, to make them feel good and to contribute to the development of their social behavior (transferred by Hsieh et al., 2004). Leisure time word is used as free time reserves in Turkish sources. However, the meaning of "empty" in terms of meaning does not exactly meet the concept of "leisure" (Özbey and Çelebi, 2003). In accordance with this thought, Kelly mentioned this; if something is being done

within the time frame, then it is not a leisure time (Kelly, 1990, Gökçe, 2008). Therefore, the concept of leisure time will be used in the study instead of the concept of leisure time.

Özbey, Güzel and Çelebi (2012) indicated the importance of recreational programs in the positive development of youth; they determined that in these activities; young people have achieved gains in self-confidence emotion, self-expression, communication, tolerance and healthy living. At this point, university learning period is the most important process of behavior patterns that will continue for years. Participation in recreational activities; (Ağaoglu and Eker, 2006) and positively affects the important processes of individuals' lives (job satisfaction, life satisfaction, family life, etc.).

In the process of transition from individuality to sociality, the process of cohabitation of the individual with the most crowded communities is seen during the student days (Balcı and İlhan, 2006). University learning is the most important process of behaviors that will last for years (Korkmaz, 2000). The students in higher education institutions have a very important place in the population of Turkey which has a young structure. Besides this, young people are the potential and trust of their sensitive and dynamic structure for the future of the country (Aybek, 2007). Every positive attitude in this process will take one step forward in happiness for the individual (Korkmaz, 2000). Ward et al. (2005) have indicated that International Students are 'so-journer' in the literature, namely 'temporary residents or students in circulation'. Ward et al. (2005) refer to 'so-journer', or 'temporary guests', who are temporarily settled for training, work or voluntary work for a period of 6 months to 5 years. International students are in a group known as very old temporary residents. The international adaptation of international students, university and residents are provided via cultural orientations and activities. When leisure time activities offered to international students at universities, it is observed that these activities are not presented regularly and programmatically. In addition to this, scientific studies on the benefits of these activities to international students are also insufficient. In general, studies evaluating international students and their free time participation in Turkey are inadequate. International students, as well as other university students have wished and expectations that they can enjoy social, cultural, sporting, and so on in order to pass the university's academic environment as well as their leisure time (Zerengök, 2016)

The concept of Quality of Life (QOL) is a thing that formed by the changing life conditions and the innovations brought by the changes in the process ranging from antiquity to these days. Although, Aristotle was the first person who, indirectly, investigated this subject. The ultimate goal in life is called Eudamania by Aristotle. This

means to be blessed with a good spirit and energy and to start living in this way (Tekkanat, 2008). Farquar (1995) reported that YK surveys, which were defined differently by researchers, have accelerated since the 1970s. In 1987, Holmes and Dickerson accepted quality of life as a dynamic concept in health (Farquhar, 1995). In 1975, as a key word in describing Patterson life quality, (Yancar, 2005) According to War (2009), quality of life is identified as perception of the position in life in relation to its aims, expectations, standards and relevance within the context of culture and value systems in which one lives. The physical health of a person is a broad concept influenced in a complex way in relation to his / her psychological state, beliefs, social relations and environment. According to Testa and Simonson (1996), quality of life includes the level of affecting the individual's physical functions, mental state, social relations within and outside the family, and how this affects the functioning of the individual. The World Health Organization defines quality of life as "the way in which people perceive their situation in the whole culture and value judgments they live in" (Zorba, 2011) in relation to their purposes, expectations, standards, it is aimed to examine the relationship between the level of life satisfaction and the level of leisure time satisfaction of foreign students who study in Turkey.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Research Model

In this study, a descriptive survey model was used. Descriptive research aims to describe the part of interest. The survey model is based on presenting the existing situation in an existing and objective manner (Karasar, 1999). Within the framework of this model, it was determined that the level of life satisfaction and free time satisfaction of foreign students studying at Erciyes University during the 2016-2017 education period were defined and then it was determined whether they shoed difference between the variances related to their personal qualities. Ultimately, the relationship between leisure time satisfaction and life satisfaction levels of students was examined.

2.2. Study Group

During the 2016-2017 academic year 220 foreign students studying at Erciyes University participated in the study voluntarily. 147 (66.8%) of the students participated in the study were male, 73 (33.2%) of them were female, 93 (42.3%) were living at home and 127 (57.7%) of the students live in dorms, from participants while 146 of them (66.4 %) doing sports, 74 of them (33.6 %) do not do sports. Again 95 of students (43.2 %) participate to sportive activities, 83 of them (37.7%) participate in social activities and 42

of them (19.1%) participate in cultural activities. Besides these, Leisure time and life satisfaction was determined as it affects 118 of the students' (53.6%) lessons positively, 37 of the students' (16.8 %) lessons negatively and 65 of the students' (29.5 %) lessons are not affected.

2.3. Data Collecting Tools

Survey technique was used as data collection tool in the research. In the first part of the research, there are 5 questions that reflect the participants' demographic information. In the second part of the study, "Leisure Time Satisfaction Scale" was used in the evaluation of the leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students study at Erciyes University. The scale was developed by Karlı and his colleagues in 2008 and used to determine the free time satisfaction levels of the students. The scale is totally consisted of 39 questions. The scale has six sub dimensions: education, physiological, aesthetic, relaxation, social and psychological. Responses given to the statements in the scale were arranged at the 5-point Likert scale. The evaluations were made (5 points for the always valid option for me, 1 point for the option that is never valid for me). In the third part of the study, the "Life Satisfaction Scale", which was developed by Diener and his colleagues in 1985, was used by Yetim in 1993 and composed of 5 items adapted to Turkish. The answers given to the scale were rated in a 7-point likert style (1 = Absolutely not agree, 7 = Absolutely Agree).

2.4. Analysis of Datum

Datum collected through Life Satisfaction and Leisure Time Satisfaction Scales were analyzed via statistical package program (SPSS.22) and the results were interpreted. Descriptive statistics including arithmetic average, standard deviation, frequency and percentage distributions were presented in order to make sure that demographic information and opinions of other group questions were acquired. Correlation (r-statistic) test was applied to determine the relationship between life satisfaction level and leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students. First, the normality of distributions (Kolmogorov-Smirnov) was examined and Mann Whitney-U and Kruskal Wallis Test were applied according to the test result in order to determine the relationship between life satisfaction level and leisure time satisfaction levels with some demographic variances. The results were evaluated at 95% reliability range and at $p < 0.05$ meaningfulness level.

3. Findings

Table 1: Comparison of life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students depending on gender variance

		Gender	N	Mean	S.s	U	P
	Life Satisfaction	Male	147	21.87	6.052	4225.000	0.01**
	General Point	Female	73	19.42	7.031		
	Leisure Time	Male	147	3.40	.566	5359.500	0.98
	General Point	Female	73	3.48	.686		
	Education	Male	147	3.39	.645	5142.500	0.61
		Female	73	3.41	.838		
	Physiological	Male	147	3.40	.678	4893.000	0.28
		Female	73	3.35	.759		
Leisure Time Satisfaction	Aesthetic	Male	147	3.20	.769	4987.000	0.39
		Female	73	3.34	.865		
Sub Dimensions	Relaxation	Male	147	3.59	.779	4754.500	0.16
		Female	73	3.76	.823		
	Social	Male	147	3.36	.647	5045.500	0.47
		Female	73	3.48	.793		
	Psychological	Male	147	3.36	.647	5140.500	0.61
		Female	73	3.59	.785		
Total			220				

**p<0.01

According to Table 1, there was a meaningful difference between the groups depending on the gender variance in the life satisfaction level of the foreign students who did not work but no significant difference between the groups according to the gender variable in the free time satisfaction levels and subscales. When the acquired statistical results are examined, it is seen that life satisfaction levels of male students of foreign countries are significantly higher than female students.

Table 2: Comparison of life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels' sub dimensions of foreign students depending on living place variance

		Where Do You Live?	N	Mean	S.s	U	P
	Life Satisfaction General Point	Home	93	21.34	6.823	5434.000	0.31
		Dorm	127	20.85	6.238		
	Leisure Time Satisfaction General Point	Home	93	3.62	.680	4065.000	0.00**
		Dorm	127	3.29	.507		
Leisure Time Satisfaction Sub Dimensions	Education	Home	93	3.63	.759	3981.500	0.00**
		Dorm	127	3.23	.627		

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Physiological	Home	93	3.48	.766	5102.500	0.08
	Dorm	127	3.31	.649		
Aesthetic	Home	93	3.43	.870	4568.000	0.00**
	Dorm	127	3.11	.724		
Relaxation	Home	93	3.90	.845	4095.500	0.00**
	Dorm	127	3.46	.707		
Social	Home	93	3.59	.757	4352.500	0.00**
	Dorm	127	3.26	.621		
Psychological	Home	93	3.71	.856	4323.500	0.00**
	Dorm	127	3.37	.705		
Total		220				

**p<0.01

According to Table 2, there was no meaningful difference found between the groups according to the place of residence at the level of life satisfaction of the foreign students who did not work, but there was a meaningful difference between the groups according to the free time satisfaction levels and the place where they reside in education, aesthetics, relaxation and social and psychological sub-dimensions. When the acquired statistical results were examined, it was seen that the level of free time satisfaction of the foreign students staying at home was significantly higher than the students staying at home.

Table 3: Comparison of life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels' sub dimensions of foreign students depending on doing sports variance

	Do you do Sports?	N	Mean	S.s	U	P
Life Satisfaction General Point	Yes	146	22.11	5.757	3982.000	0.00**
	No	74	18.97	7.316		
Leisure Time Satisfaction General Point	Yes	146	3.51	.577	4122.000	0.00**
	No	74	3.28	.641		
Education	Yes	146	3.45	.671	4582.000	0.06
	No	74	3.28	.781		
Physiological	Yes	146	3.51	.704	3567.500	0.00**
	No	74	3.13	.639		
Aesthetic	Yes	146	3.26	.803	5232.500	0.70
	No	74	3.21	.809		
Relaxation	Yes	146	3.69	.803	4770.500	0.15
	No	74	3.55	.779		
Social	Yes	146	3.49	.663	4188.500	0.00**
	No	74	3.23	.742		
Psychological	Yes	146	3.61	.754	4227.500	0.00**

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	No	74	3.32	.824
Total	220			

**p<0.01

According to Table 3, there was a significant difference found between the groups according to life satisfaction levels, leisure time satisfaction levels and sporting status in physiological, social and psychological subscales of foreign students who were not employed. When the obtained statistical results were examined, it was seen that the life satisfaction and free time satisfaction levels of the foreign national students who do sports were significantly higher than the ones that do not do sports students.

Table 4: Comparison of life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels' sub dimensions of foreign students depending on participated activity type variance

		Which Activities Do you Participate?	N	Mean	Sd	X ²	P
Life Satisfaction General Point		Sportive Activities	95	22.28			
		Social Activities	83	20.68	2	7.488	0.02
		Cultural Activities	42	19.02			
Leisure Time Satisfaction General Point		Sportive Activities	95	3.52			
		Social Activities	83	3.38	2	6.483	0.03
		Cultural Activities	42	3.32			
Education		Sportive Activities	95	3.56			
		Social Activities	83	3.29	2	11.509	0.00**
		Cultural Activities	42	3.25			
Physiological		Sportive Activities	95	3.57			
		Social Activities	83	3.22	2	14.220	0.00**
		Cultural Activities	42	3.26			
Aesthetic		Sportive Activities	95	3.28			
		Social Activities	83	3.22	2	.506	0.77
		Cultural Activities	42	3.22			
Relaxation		Sportive Activities	95	3.71			
		Social Activities	83	3.65	2	2.430	0.29
		Cultural Activities	42	3.50			
Social		Sportive Activities	95	3.44			
		Social Activities	83	3.41	2	2.045	0.36
		Cultural Activities	42	3.28			
Psychological		Sportive Activities	95	3.53			
		Social Activities	83	3.53	2	.872	0.64
		Cultural Activities	42	3.44			
Total			220				

p<0.05 **p<0.01

According to Table 4, there was an important difference found between the groups depending on the level of life satisfaction, leisure time satisfaction level and the type of activity they participated in education and physiological sub-dimensions of foreign students who were not working. When the acquired statistical results were examined, it was seen that the life satisfaction and free time satisfaction levels of the foreign students participating in sports activities were meaningfully higher than those participating in other activity types.

Table 5: Comparison of effect of life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students' lessons

	How they affect your lessons?	N	Mean	Sd	X ²	P
Life Satisfaction General Point	Positive	118	21.95			
	Negative	37	19.18	2	6.698	0.03
	Do not Affect	65	20.49			
Leisure Time Satisfaction General Point	Positive	118	3.58			
	Negative	37	3.13	2	23.397	0.00**
	Do not Affect	65	3.32			
Total		220				

p<0.05 **p<0.01

According to Table 5, there was a meaningful difference found between the groups according to the life satisfaction levels of the foreign students working and the variances that affect the courses of the leisure time satisfaction levels. When the obtained statistical results are examined, it is seen that life satisfaction and leisure time satisfaction levels have positive effects on the students' classes.

Table 6: Relationship between life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students

	Life Satisfaction		
Leisure Time Satisfaction	r	1	.307
	p	-	0.00***
	n	220	-

***p<0.001

According to Table 6, there was a positive relationship found between life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students who participated to study (p <0.05, r = 0.307). According to this result, as the level of satisfaction of foreign students' increases, the level of life satisfaction also increases.

4. Result

According to Table 1, there was a meaningful difference between the groups depending on the gender variable in the life satisfaction level of the foreign students participating in the study, but no significant difference was found between the groups according to the gender variable in the free time satisfaction levels and subscales. When the acquired statistical results were examined, it was seen that life satisfaction levels of foreign students were importantly higher than female students.

When the body of literature was examined and relationship between gender variance and leisure time satisfaction considered while results of the study conducted by Ardahan and Yerlisu Lapa (2010), Lu and Hu (2005), VongTze (2005) and Ayyıldız (2015), and the results of this study showing parallelism; In Serdar's master thesis (2016) University Students' Satisfaction with Leisure Time Activities and Perceived Freedom Levels showed a significant difference in gender variance. Mehmet Akif Ersoy University students were found to have statistically meaningful differences in their participation in leisure time exercises in order to determine whether they differed significantly according to sex. Male participants were more likely to participate in exhaustion than female participants. (Karaca) Yine Sönmezoğlu et al. (2014), the results of this study are not parallel with each other. When the relationship between gender variance and life satisfaction were examined; Examination of the relationship between physical activity level and quality of life of university personnel (2013) university graduates showed that physical activity levels were higher in male university students compared to women in the graduate thesis and in studies of Baş Aslan (2003), Savcı and his friends (2006) (2011) and Deniz (2011). When the quality of life points of the individuals were compared, it was found that the average of all the subscales of the life quality of the male subjects and the summary scores had higher values than the average scores of the female subscales and summary scores of the life quality. Similarly, there was a higher level of quality of life scores in men than in women (Tekkanat, 2008), in a study on the quality of life and physical activity levels of the students study in the teaching profession. In another study on elderly individuals, a similar result was also obtained (Acreeand et al, 2006).

According to Table 2, there were no meaningful differences found among the groups according to the place of dwelling at the level of life satisfaction of the foreign students who participated in the study, but there was a significant difference between the groups according to the level of leisure time satisfaction and the place where they reside in education, aesthetics, relaxation, social and psychological sub dimensions. When the obtained statistical results were examined, it was seen that the level of leisure

time satisfaction of the foreign students staying at home was importantly higher than the students who live at home.

When the body of literature is examined in the, it is seen that the leisure time and the housing sub-dimension are not compared in the previous studies in the field of summer when the relationship between the housing change and free time satisfaction is considered and it is thought that this study will be an example for later studies. When the quality of life and the quality of life were compared, Özgür et al. (2010), Life Satisfaction in University Students Living at Home and Dorms is very high for those students staying at home who are "very satisfied" and evaluate their quality of life as "good". Similar results were found in the students living in the country and it was determined that the life satisfaction of the students who are not satisfied with living in the country is at the worse situation. Similar results have been found in other studies that have indicated the effect of life-satisfaction on the living conditions of residents (Ashand Huebner, 2001., Foubergand et al, 1997). Also in Tekkanat's master thesis (2008) Department of Teaching, Life Quality and Physical Activity Levels there was meaningfully result and higher than those in the residents, except for the spiritual area in the students living at home. This finding can be interpreted as the higher quality of life of the students staying at home. It can be considered that the residents are likely to have less satisfaction with the physical and social conditions at home than those living at home, and the conditions in the country should be examined in this context. Also, students who are living at home may have been more casual as they are creating their own living styles. These studies do not show parallelism with our study.

According to Table 3, there was a meaningful difference between the groups according to life satisfaction levels, leisure time satisfaction levels and sporting status in physiological, social and psychological subscales of foreign students participating in the study. When the acquired statistical results were examined, it was seen that the life satisfaction and leisure time satisfaction levels of the foreign national students who do sports were significantly higher than the ones that do not do sports.

When the body of literature is examined the relationship between sporting change and free time satisfaction is considered, In Serdar' master thesis about (2016) Student Satisfaction with Satisfaction with Free Time Activities and Perceived Freedom Levels. There was no meaningful difference found between the two groups. This work does not support my work. When we examine the relationship between sporting variables and quality of life, Özüdoğru (2013) Examination of the Relationship between Physical Activity Level and Quality of Life of University Personnel in the mentioned master's thesis "In answer to the question" Are there any differences between the quality of life and physical activity levels of academic and administrative personnel?

When the quality of life was compared according to the physical activity levels of the staff, there was generally a significant difference seen. The quality of life scores of amputee athletes were found to be statistically higher at the level of $p < 0,01$ significance than the values of amputees in the named master's thesis by Yazıcı (2012), in the statistical examination of the Quality of Life and Depressive Situations of the Amputee Individuals Who Play and Do not Play. The conducted studies are in the quality of supporting our study.

According to Table 4, there was a meaningful difference between the groups according to the level of life satisfaction, leisure time satisfaction level and the type of activity they attended in education and physiological sub-dimensions of foreign students participating in the study. When the obtained statistical results were examined, it was seen that the life satisfaction and free time satisfaction levels of the foreign students participating in sports activities were meaningfully higher than those participating in other activity types.

When the body of literature was examined, it was found that in Serdar's master thesis about (2016) University Students' Satisfaction with Free Time Activities and Perceived Freedom Levels were found. As a result of the obtained findings, according to the participation patterns of the students in the artistic / cultural activities the active participants in the physiological sub-dimension in terms of their leisure time satisfaction levels are more significant scores than the passive participants. In the case of the graduate thesis with "Quality of Life and Depressive Situations of the Amputee Individuals with and without Sports" topic (2012), there was no statistically significant difference found between the groups in terms of the total quality of life scores of Amputee athletes compared to the cinema and theater, there are statistically significant differences between the two groups in terms of the number of times the scores are passed to the cinema and the theater, between once every two weeks and never, sometimes never, and several times a year. We can say that these studies are in the quality of supporting our study.

According to Table 5, there was a significant difference found between the groups according to the life satisfaction levels of the foreign students participating in the study and the variables affecting the courses of the free time satisfaction levels. When the statistical results obtained are evaluated, it is seen that life satisfaction and free time satisfaction levels have positive effects on the students' lessons.

When we take a look on the relationship between variables and free time satisfaction, we found no evidence of course change and course quality of life quality. However, when we consider social, psychological and physical influences on sports

people, we think that sports are influenced positively by these effects and we think that this study will be an example of the studies that are going to be done in the future.

According to Table 6, there was a positive relationship between life satisfaction levels and leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students participating in the study ($p < 0.05$, $r = 0.307$). According to this result, as the leisure time satisfaction levels of foreign students increases, life satisfaction levels also increases.

When the body of literature was examined, there was no study done between leisure time and life satisfaction. When we examine the conducted studies, we see that the life satisfaction is compared with the physical activity rather than the free time and that these studies are more focused. In this context, Yayan and Altun (2013) found that the life quality of the students who did sports on adolescents was high (Yayan and Altun, 2013). Genç et al. (2011) found that male and female young adults had higher levels of total physical activity and higher quality of life in men compared to women in terms of their participation in physical activity and determining their quality of life differences (Genç et al., 2011). Çamlıyer et al. (1999) found that participation in sport activities positively contributed positively to the social development of adolescents (Çamlıyer et al., 1999) in their study of the effects of sports activities on the level of social development in children and adolescents. Montenegro's (2008) study of adolescents in rural areas to examine the relationship between psychological symptoms and quality of life according to their level of physical activity has found that as adolescents increase their time to play sports, the severity of psychiatric symptoms decreases and quality of life scores and the number of hours they spend with their friends increase. These studies are in the quality of supporting our work.

In this study, the relationship between the levels of life satisfaction and leisure time satisfaction of foreign students study at Erciyes University was. Some suggestions can be made for the studies that will be done later by going out of the field and not working. These are; this study covers only one university, but the studies to be done can be done at more than one university and these universities can be compared according to various characteristics. Besides this, foreign students study at state and private universities can be included in future researches.

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